

LEXICAL ISSUES IN TRANSLATION THEORY AND COMMON WAYS OF OVERCOMING THEM

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Abstract: *This article will discuss common lexical problems which give a rise during translation study. As the translation field incorporated into the curriculum of students, its difficulties cannot be avoided and thus should be suppressed with several lexical transformations, which will be described in the article as well*

Keywords: *lexical issues, lexical substitution, inexpressibility of words, realias.*

Each language is a deeply original, specific phenomenon. The meaning is conveyed using translation correspondences, which have a different linguistic expression, a different set of semes, which requires different translation transformations. Translation from Russian into English is fraught with many difficulties. One of them is a different vision of the world and the associated linguistic selectivity. The Russian language is characterized by a large number of long polysyllabic words, while in English, on the contrary, short monosyllabic words predominate. In English, verb forms are more often used, while in Russian, nominal forms are used. The Russian language is more emotional, while English is more pragmatic.

Let's look at some of the most common difficulties that arise when translating vocabulary from Russian into English.

1. Many terms accepted for use in the political Russian language are distinguished by their emotionality, stylistic overtones and may turn out to be "false friends of the translator", for example: revolution – revolution differ not only in the fact that in English the turnover has a meaning, but also in the assessment. In Russian, the word revolution takes on a radical character and always denotes progress in change, while in English the word has both progressive and regressive connotations.

2. Often Russian military terms require descriptive translation into English. Military metaphors and terms are familiar to Russian people, but among foreigners

they evoke a feeling of Russian aggressiveness. Over the course of Soviet rule, their number decreased, but they still remain, which is why it is recommended to replace them with neutral words. In addition, in political Russian texts a large number of terms that are not in English require descriptive translation: sequester – budget cuts

3. When translating into English, it is necessary to pay special attention to the translation of abbreviations; you also need to be well aware of the established names of international organizations and positions and not translate them literally. For example: UN Secretary General. Moreover, it is necessary to know the abbreviations and not translate them back, as this can lead to fundamental distortion of information, for example: OSCE – OSCE (Organization on Security and Cooperation in Europe).

4. In political vocabulary there is a large number of clichés that you just need to know to translate. However, it should be remembered that the same term can take on different meanings depending on the context. For example: hotbed of tension, task – goal, task, aim, purpose, objection.

5. Great difficulties are caused by the translation of realities – these are concepts related to life, everyday life and are absent in the language systems of other people, for example: region – область. Realities are often conveyed through transcription, transliteration and tracing, or through description, for example: дача- summer house. Realities serve to convey expression, and since explanations lengthen the text, they sometimes resort to generalization, specification, or semantic development.

6. During the period of Soviet power, many so-called Sovietisms appeared, they also require description and explanation when translated, for example: machine operator – machine operator. When compounding words during translation, they are expanded into a phrase, for example: scientific and pedagogical personnel – teaching and scientific staff.

7. A special place in translation is given to verbal nouns, which abound in Russian-language texts; such words require significant transformation during translation. They can be translated by nouns, infinitives, a combination of a preposition with a gerund, a gerund, and sometimes, if they are insignificant, they can be omitted during translation. The Russian language is characterized by substantivization of actions and processes; verbal nouns are used in the position of subject, object, circumstance, and when translated into English a number of transformations are required. It is recommended to replace an abstract noun with a concrete one

8. Translation of phraseological units also requires a special approach. In Russian, phraseological units are more emotional than in English. They are often weakened when translated into English. The same concept can be presented with varying degrees of colloquialism and evaluation. In the Russian language, peripheral

vocabulary is widely used, outdated, which is practically absent in English, for example: not so hot – not all that well. In English, as mentioned earlier, they are extremely rare, for example: willy–nilly- волей-неволей.

English phraseology is often associated with the Bible and sports, so to translate it you need to be familiar with the topic. To translate phraseological units, substitutions, tracings, analogues, equivalents or descriptive translation are used. If Russian phraseology is full of archaic expressions, then English phraseology is full of slang. Among phraseological units you can also find “false friends of the translator” – they coincide in the composition of the components, but differ in meaning, for example: to lead by the nose (to deceive) – to lead by the nose (to completely subjugate). Thus, to translate a phraseological unit, it is necessary to select the components of the semantic structure of the original and select the closest equivalent, using, if possible, the same techniques.

In addition to the above, it is necessary not to forget that verbs borrowed from Latin or Greek are often used in the Russian language. They are present in English, but there they create the effect of text heaviness and formality. When translating into Russian, it is better to use short phrases with postpositions, for example: compensate – make up for somebody

There are principal types of lexical correspondences between 2 languages: 1) complete, 2) partial, 3) an absence of correspondence

Complete correspondence can not be found always, due to its complexity and it only make translation with the terms related to geographical names, science and technology, the months and days of the week, numerals.

Partial correspondences are usually in use, in this way of rendering, translator look at the words, which have identical meaning in the TL as well as recognise and pick up the mostly suitable one

Following ways of rendering:

1. Substitution

Concrete definition – replacing a word with a broad sense by one of a narrower, she is in the kitchen – она ГОТОВИТ

Generalization- replacing a word’s narrow meaning by one with a broad sense: A Oolong tea – китайский чай;

An integral transformation: How is it going – Как дела?

Antonymous transformation is a lexical substitution of any word with negative meaning or vice versa

2. **Supplementation** – addition of extra elements to the words, which are inexpressible: Pay claim – требование о выплате

3. **Omitting** – words with surplus meaning are usually removed, to pull one's nose – дурачить

Absence of correspondences usually appears, when it is impossible to find analogs or equivalents for the words, which interferred in the SL, for instance, it is always the case with realia

Realias – are the linguistic units related to objects, phenomenon and reflect a national life, culture and identity of a particular country

Conclusion

Thus, all of the above suggests that the translator must strive to preserve the original. At the same time, we should not forget that some expressions are familiar in one language and completely unusual in another. The main thing to strive for is to convey the image and intention of the original.

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